

GENERATIVE WORDS OF ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH SENTENCE

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Abstract:

This aim of the research is to investigate the generative “morphemes, words or “simple or compoundⁱⁱ” sentence. The full contrast of Albanian and English language in these phenomena of generative is in morphology and in syntactic structure. This accepts of studies will **comported**, **contrasted** and **generated** between two languages. This studies deals with noun (noun phrase), verb (verb phrase) of syntactic structure between Albanian and English language. In both of languages, most linguists (or scholars) are agree because has the contrast between Alb. – Eng. The following classes words: **noun**, **verb**, **adjective**, **preposition**, **adverb**, **determinative** and **conjunction** can generate. Each of these words classes is illustrated in the sentence below. The function of noun (or noun phrase) in the sentence can have the meaning of **subjectⁱⁱⁱ**, **direct object^{iv}**, **indirect object^v** and **“predicate”** (...). The function of verb or verb phrase in the sentence can have the predicate (...).

Keywords: generative morpheme, words, simple or compound sentence; Albanian and English language

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ⁱⁱⁱ Shkelqim Millaku, THE FUNCTION OF ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH SENTENCE, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/830/2369>

^{iv} Shkelqim Millaku, The direct object, ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, Volume 4, issue 1, 2015, e-ISSN: 1857-8187 p-ISSN: 1857-8179, <http://www.anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>

^v Shkelqim Millaku, THE INDIRECT OBJECT (IO) – ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 – 1754, <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/294/739>

Introduction

We may begin our inquiry into the study of syntax between Albanian and English. Both of languages have their rules of structures that we will do or see “in this paper” the **contrast**^{vi}, (compare) and during the studies, we can see the different or same structure between both of them. The aim of studies is to generate. They (both of languages) have same **subject, (direct or indirect) object**^{vii}, **predicate**, etc., but different (morphology) structure (in the using or position the words in the sentence). There are four (some) main types of sentences: **simple, compound**^{viii}, **complex and compound complex**.

The scholar or the author Graeme Kennedy (2003) for the noun phrases said: “A phrase is a unit of analysis smaller than a sentence and consisting of a single word or group of words. A phrase is associated with, or is an expansion of, the word class of its most important constituent (in the headword)”^{ix}.

This phenomena of studies was research the first by Harris (1951) and was take up by Chomsky (1957-70), Fillmore (1968), Marchand (1969), Rohrer (1974), Jackendoff (1977), Muysken (1985), Leonad Newmark (1982), etc.; by Albanian scholars: Rami Memushaj, Dalina Kallulli, Josif Mita etc.

The generative^x studies for compound aren't doing as possible as like. So, we would like in the following to show two examples in Albanian and English. In Albanian language, the compound noun can generative in this form (bregdet^{xi} and kryeqytet^{xii}):

^{vi} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST AND THE FUNCTION OF THE GENDER ALBANIAN TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/829/2366>

^{vii} Shkelqim Millaku, The direct object, ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, Volume 4, issue 1, 2015, e-ISSN: 1857-8187, p-ISSN: 1857-8179, <http://www.anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>

^{viii} Shkelqim Millaku, THE COMPOUND IN “ALBANIAN LANGUAGE DICTIONARY” OF MEHMET ELEZI, European Journal of Education Studies ISSN: 2501 - 1111 ISSN-L: 2501 - 1111 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/889>

^{ix} Graeme Kennedy. (2003). Structure and meaning in English, Great Britain, p. 112.

^x Shkelqim Millaku, INCLUSION AND THE HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE ALBANIAN GENERATIVE CONCEPTS, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754, <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/1139/3304>

^{xi} Shkelqim Millaku, THE FUNCTION OF ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH SENTENCE, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/830/2369>

^{xii} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPOUND WORDS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051614

The first diagram of the compound^{xiii} noun is noun + noun = noun, “its compound noun” by breg (height) and det (sea). The first word *height* (by the electronic dictionary, we have this comment): “is the measurement of someone or something from head to foot or from base to top. The quality of begin tall or high. Elevation above (typically sea level). A high place or area. The most intense part or period of something or example of something: the height of badmanners” but in Albanian for the word breg we have this comment “që është pjesë rrip toke që kufizon në anë një rrjedhë uji, një det, një liqen etj. Anë toke që ndodhet buzë një sipërfaqeje uji”.^{xiv} The second noun has this meaning in dictionary: The expanse of salt water that covers most of them earth’s surface and surrounds its land masses. A roughly definable area of this: The black sea etc., but in Albanian we have this comment for the word det: “hapësirë shumë e madhe më ujë të kripur që zakonisht është e rrethuar me tokë jo nga të gjitha anët dhe që qëndron disi e veçuar, pjesa më e madhe e rruzullit tokësor, e mbuluar me ujë të kripur”.^{xv} Both of them breg + det have creative the new word with the new meaning bregdet – beach and this word beach has this meaning for example: A pebbly or sandy shore at the edge of the sea or a lake. Bring on to a beach from the water, become or cause to become stranded on a beach.

Another model or tip that we have studied during our research is for example compound + affixes e.g. bashkëkohës^{xvi}, zëvendës, kryengritje, (ngre kryet) etc. The Albanian words “zëvendës^{xvii}, kryengritje” we would like to generative e.g.

^{xiii} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPOUND WORDS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051614

^{xiv} Fjalori elektronik shpjegues, FESH 1.0.

^{xv} Ibidem, F.E.SH.

^{xvi} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPOUND WORDS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051614

^{xvii} Shkelqim Millaku, THE COMPOUND IN “ALBANIAN LANGUAGE DICTIONARY” OF MEHMET ELEZI, European Journal of Education Studies ISSN: 2501 - 1111 ISSN-L: 2501 - 1111 Available on-line at: <https://edu.oapub.org/index.php/ejes/article/view/889/2546>

The third diagram has compound + affixes (suffixes) that in fact has creative the new word with the new meaning. The generative of the Albanian word /zëvendës/ it's possible to see the origine of them. **Zëvendës**^{xviii} comes by **zë-** as a **verb** and **noun + -vend = noun** and **suffixes -ës**, both of them have creative the new word with new meaning. In the fourth diagram we can see: **noun + verb + suffix - (krye + ngrit -je = kryengritje**^{xix}). The English language can has this form of generative like with compund words "**housekeeper**^{xx} and **scholbook**.

^{xviii} Shkelqim Millaku, THE COMPOUND IN "ALBANIAN LANGUAGE DICTIONARY" OF MEHMET ELEZI, European Journal of Education Studies ISSN: 2501 - 1111 ISSN-L: 2501 - 1111 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/889>

^{xix} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPOUND WORDS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051614

^{xx} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPOUND WORDS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051614

^{xxi} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPOUND WORDS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051614

The generative^{xxii} and the origin of English words are by N. Chomsky in his book “Syntactic Structure, 1957” has description correctly this phenomena. After him has done a lot of study for English but not as so much for Albanian. The compound words “housekeeper” and “schoolbook” are made by noun + noun + suffixes –er and the word schoolbook is make by noun + noun. Both of them have creative the new words with the new meaning. By this massage of the sentence, we cannot see^{xxiii} a lot of difference between both of languages. Two noun phrases^{xxiv} can be coordinated with simple words or with phase, like with:

In Albanian language, in this way is possible to generate^{xxv} simple and compound sentence^{xxvi}, like with: **“Studenti kishte takuar profesorin para provimit”**. It can generate with the diagram and the noun is the head (S) of the sentence. The (follow) tree of diagram is studied by **Josif Mita**^{xxvii} e.g.

^{xxii} Shkelqim Millaku, INCLUSION AND THE HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE ALBANIAN GENERATIVE CONCEPTS, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754, <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/1139/3304>

^{xxiii} Shkelqim Millaku, THE FUNCTION OF ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH SENTENCE, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/830/2369>

^{xxiv} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPOUND WORDS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>

^{xxv} Shkelqim Millaku, INCLUSION AND THE HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE ALBANIAN GENERATIVE CONCEPTS, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754, <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/1139/3304>

^{xxvi} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPOUND WORDS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: www.oapub.org/edu, <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>

^{xxvii} Josif Mita. (2008). Rendi i fjalëve dhe struktura e fjalëve kohore. Prishtinë, p. 13.

Fig. 9

This diagram is opposite with the Chomsky message. This study is impossible to have the meaning because the first this is simple sentence and it needs to generation with the form NP + VP - NP or the right tree for this sentence is more possible this on:

Fig. 10

As we said before the noun is the head of sentence, because it can be a **subject, direct and indirect object** etc e.g. **Studenti^{xxviii} kishte takuar profesorin para provimit.**

S P IO^{xxix} DO^{xxx}

^{xxviii} Shkelqim Millaku, THE FUNCTION OF ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH SENTENCE, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/830/2369>

^{xxix} Shkelqim Millaku, THE INDIRECT OBJECT (IO) – ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 – 1754, <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/294>

^{xxx} Shkelqim Millaku, The direct object, ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, Volume 4, issue 1, 2015 • e-ISSN: 1857-8187 • p-ISSN: 1857-8179, <http://www.anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>

The Albanian sentence “Kur deti egërsohej peshkatarët rrinin në shtëpi”

SE + (FN) + SF+S' → S'+SE+ (FN) +SF
 1 2 → 2 1

I think this diagram is not correct because it is the compound sentence. The symbol **Fj** need to be **P.N.k.** (periudhë -**P** – compound sentence and nënrenditur -**N** -suborder, kohore -**k** - time), after **SE** “peshkatarët” cannot stay in the middle of the diagram. The **SF** cannot be there but I think it is the second sentence (**Fj2**). I think the correct analyse for this diagram is:

The Albanian compound^{xxxi} sentence “**Nëna gëzohej që i ishte bërë vajza për shkollë**” is possible to generate^{xxxii} in this way: P.F.N.sh (Fj1 – SE + SF – që - Fj2 SF+SE)

^{xxxi} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPOUND WORDS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051614

^{xxxii} Shkelqim Millaku, INCLUSION AND THE HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE ALBANIAN GENERATIVE CONCEPTS, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754, <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/1139/3304>

The same diagram is possible to have:

^{xxxiii} This diagram is personated during the speech by Prof. dr. Ruzhdi Ushaku

The Albanian compound sentence^{xxxiv} **Ushtarët u ulën, ndezën zjarrin dhe** *disa* **zunë të hanë nga strajca që kishin më vete''** can generate in this diagram:

^{xxxiv} Shkelqim Millaku, THE FUNCTION OF ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH SENTENCE, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/830/2369>

The next Albanian sentence can generate^{xxxv} as: **Kanë parë Agimin *dhe* kanë përshendetur**

Luanin: Kanë parë Agimin *dhe* kanë përshendetur Luanin.

The last diagram was presented by Josif Mita at his book “Hyrje në sintaksën gjenerative” f. 210, but I think the correct way for to present is:

^{xxxv} Shkelqim Millaku, INCLUSION AND THE HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE ALBANIAN GENERATIVE CONCEPTS, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754, <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/1139/3304>

The sentence “**People know voters prefer results**” has this notation: the rules isolated in the preceding paragraph can be stated as follows:

- $S \rightarrow NP^{xxxvi} VP$
- $NP \rightarrow N$
- $NP \rightarrow S$
- $N \rightarrow \text{people, voters, results}$
- $V \rightarrow \text{know, prefer}^{xxxvii}$.

The diagram of the notation of the sentence is:

^{xxxvi} Shkelqim Millaku, The direct object, ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, Volume 4, issue 1, 2015 • e-ISSN: 1857-8187 • p-ISSN: 1857-8179, <http://www.anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>

^{xxxvii} Shkelqim Millaku, THE FUNCTION OF ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH SENTENCE, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/830/2369>

The rules of Albanian and English grammar can be considered to description which assigns the structure or diagram. The noun phrase^{xxxviii} in English and Albanian is more productive if we study and respect the rules of generative and diagrams, too. The contrast of genitive^{xxxix} between Albanian and English (word) can be in the sentence at the beginning, middle or in the end. The tree or diagram^{xl} of the simple sentence can follow the genitive that is in the beginning of sentence:

^{xxxviii} Shkelqim Millaku, THE FUNCTION OF NOUN PHRASES BETWEEN ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH,
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051611

^{xxxix} Shkelqim Millaku, The contrast of the gender between Albanian and English language,
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3041938

^{xl} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST AND THE FUNCTION OF THE GENDER ALBANIAN TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE,
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<https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/829/2366>

The students' hands the teacher their quizzes^{xli}

Fig.20

This diagram of the sentence “**The students’ hands the teacher their quizzes**” the genitive^{xliv} is the subject “the students’ ”and it is not correct with the indirect object, because it needs to be one tree by noun phrase^{xlv} and from it to generate direct or indirect object.

Conclusion

The generated of words and simple or compound^{xlvi} sentence are presented by symbols and the function of them. The Albanian language and English in these phenomena has some contrast. We have analysed twenty examples.

^{xli}Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST AND THE FUNCTION OF THE GENDER ALBANIAN TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/829/2366>

^{xlii} Shkelqim Millaku, The direct object, ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, Volume 4, issue 1, 2015 • e-ISSN: 1857-8187 • p-ISSN: 1857-8179, <http://www.anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>

^{xliii} Max Morenberg. (2002). Doing Grammar. New York, p. 43.

^{xliv} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST AND THE FUNCTION OF THE GENDER ALBANIAN TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/829/2366>

^{xlv} Shkelqim Millaku, The Nominal Clauses of English and Albanian Language, Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research (IJIR) Vol-3, Issue-8, 2017 ISSN: 2454-1362, <http://www.onlinejournal.in>, <http://www.imperialjournals.com/index.php/IJIR/article/viewFile/5472/5264>

^{xlvi} Shkelqim Millaku, THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPOUND WORDS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051614

The history of generative grammar has started by Chomsky (1957, with his book *Syntactic Structure*). After some years in 1970s exploited tree diagrams that the subject (called the noun phrase), the predicate (called the verb phrase). The symbol S stands for sentence and subject, too. The generative grammar of Albanian language has basics by the 1980s or 90s. The authors which have done their contribution in this area are Rami Memushaj, Dalina Kallulli, Josif Mita etc. Our study is compared, generated between Albanian and English. The symbols between two languages are different. The noun or verb in the function of the syntax, generally don't have more difference between both of languages. In Albanian the noun can make subject, direct or indirect object etc, same can do and in English. The verb has a function of predicate. The full contrast we can see in the structure of morphology.

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